

PROPENSITY TO ACT AND ENTREPRENEURIAL INTENTIONS: THE IMPACT OF SELF-EFFICACY AMONG SME OWNERS

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ABSTRACT	KEYWORDS
<p>This study focused on the effect of entrepreneurial self-efficacy on entrepreneurial intentions of SME owners from the perspective of propensity to act. The study employed survey research design. The study used a 336-participants sample size. Both descriptive and inferential analytical techniques were used to analyze the study's data. Multiple regression analysis is the basic analytical method that was used. Finding showed that self-efficacy has effect on the propensity to act of SME Owners in Edo State. The study concluded that entrepreneurial self-efficacy can stimulate the propensity to act of SME Owners in Edo State. Self-efficacy has an impact on SME owners' willingness to act. Information alertness, planning under uncertainty, financial management capability, marketing ability, managerial competence, innovation capability, risk-taking capability, and critical thinking are all factors that influence SME Owners' willingness to act in Edo State. The study recommended that SMEDAN should prioritize the need for consistent entrepreneurial self-efficacy for SME owners to increase their level of propensity to act in Edo State.</p>	<p>Entrepreneurial Self-Efficacy, Entrepreneurial Intentions, Propensity to Act, Information Alertness, Innovation Capability</p>

Introduction

Today, most countries heavily support entrepreneurship. It is a well-known reality that there are enormous opportunities that people can take advantage of to further their own and the country's development. Doanh and Bernat (2019) claimed that entrepreneurship has spread globally due to its beneficial effects on global economic development. For individuals, entrepreneurship turns into a purposeful source of support. The use of technology to foster greater innovation and creativity is one of entrepreneurship's advantages for both individuals and the entire country. According to Guerrero, Rialp, and Urbano (2008), entrepreneurship is known for its innovative and creative processes (which have the prospects to add new value to products and services), increased productivity, the creation of new jobs, the revitalization and diversification of markets, the enhancement of social welfare, and the growth of the national economy.

Research into the entrepreneurial self-efficacy of individuals in Edo State is of great importance. Entrepreneurial self-efficacy promotes the awareness of individuals in the business environment, mental alertness, and social interaction with network hubs. Vital components of entrepreneurial self-efficacy in Edo State are

entrepreneurship training, entrepreneurship education and role modelling among others. Through entrepreneurial self-efficacy, individuals can possess capabilities relative to critical thinking, information alertness, planning under uncertainty, financial management capability, marketing ability, innovation and risk-taking. These are expected to create high sense of responsibility, propensity to act and willingness to take entrepreneurial risk and succeed.

The entrepreneurial self-efficacy of SME owners appears to have influenced their intentions to venture in business in Edo State. In this study, the entrepreneurial intentions of SME owners was considered from the perspective of propensity to act. It is however unclear about how entrepreneurial self-efficacy causes variations in propensity to act in Edo State. Doanh and Bernat (2019) argued that it is good predictor. Research into entrepreneurial self-efficacy and entrepreneurial intentions of SME owners in Edo State has gained less attention.

Literature Review

Conceptual Review

An important concept for evaluating entrepreneurial success is "entrepreneurial self-efficacy," and a large body of research shows that it has an impact on people's intentions to launch new businesses. Numerous definitions of entrepreneurial self-efficacy have been found in the literature. Self-efficacy is a concept that has been utilized repeatedly as an independent variable in psychology. Self-efficacy is described in one line of research as an entrepreneur's task-specific selfconfidence. Cardon and Kirk (2015) showed that entrepreneurs are more likely to carry out the tasks necessary for the creation of a new firm and to keep trying until they succeed if they have confidence in their capacity to do so. In contrast to this, several other researchers define self-efficacy as the ability to master the necessary cognitive, memory processing, and behavioural facilities to deal effectively with the environment.

Entrepreneurial self-efficacy is assessed both explicitly and implicitly (Weldy & Turnipseed, 2010). While explicit measures is of the perspectives that knowledge has been obtained, implicit measures such as surveys and interviews are used to strengthening perception (Mozahem, & Adlouni, 2020). Entrepreneurship is particularly important, as enthusiasm in the subject has grown. Despite this surge, the field has only achieved a fraction of credibility, with some educators bemoaning the existing "state-of-the-art" (Gedeon, 2014) and others even questioning whether entrepreneurship is a learning process (Neck & Greene, 2011). This issue is exacerbated by the fact that very few researches have examined entrepreneurship as a learning process in general (Warhuus & Basaiawmoit, 2014), and those that have generated a range of outcomes (Karlsson & Moberg, 2013).

A person's self-efficacy as an entrepreneur is defined as his or her confidence in one's own abilities and skills. It is described as the capacity to alter a person's belief in his or her capacity to successfully introduce and establish a new business venture. A person's confidence in his/her own entrepreneurial skills and abilities is known as entrepreneurial self-efficacy (Barakat, Boddington, & Vyakarnam, 2014). Entrepreneurial self-efficacy measures a person's confidence in his/her capacity to take the necessary steps to launch a business (Alammari, Newbery, Haddoud, & Beaumont, 2019). It is one of the most essential personal qualities influencing the abilities and chances of entrepreneurs, as it is a must for these individuals to persevere in their everyday operations and reach their objectives.

Literature has shown many dimensions of entrepreneurial self-efficacy. Ribeiro, Lopes, Fernandes and Diniz (2019) identified five dimensions ranging from new product development or new market opportunities, human resources development, investment initiative, innovation and ability to work under stress. The dimensions

identified by Mozahem and Adlouni (2020) are very important to this study. This is because the dimensions are adopted from the systematic review of several other studies.

Individuals' willingness to start up new venture will often drive in Entrepreneurial behaviour. Interest in entrepreneurship, according to Ayodele (2013), is a strong determinant of future entrepreneurial behaviour. This transcends into the concept of entrepreneurial intention. The concept of entrepreneurial intention has been attracting increased research attention for a long time now. Fayolle and Linan (2014) stated that the body of researches on the concept of entrepreneurial intent has risen, spawning a new field of study.

Entrepreneurial intention is a key concept in the literature on the subject and is frequently observed in research on entrepreneurial behavior. Different perspectives of the idea exist. According to Thompson (2009), it is a self-admitted conviction by a person who wants to launch a new entrepreneurial endeavor and deliberately plans to do so at a specific point in the future. Entrepreneurial intention is described as a "self-acknowledged conviction" by any individuals that they are willing to start a new commercial enterprise and that they have ongoing plans to do so in the future (Ridha & Wahyu, 2017). The phrase "self-acknowledged conviction" simply refers to a high level of individual capacity for taking chances and overcoming obstacles in the business world.

In Shapero's SEE model, emphasis was laid on "perceived feasibility, perceived desirability, and propensity to act" as constructs of entrepreneurial intentions. These were seen as being critical to explaining why individuals develop entrepreneurial intentions. Perceived desirability can be defined as a strong attractiveness towards a business venture, while perceived feasibility refers to individuals' confidence in starting a business, and propensity to act refers to individuals' willingness to take action based on opportunities (Sesen, 2013).

Empirical review

Lubada, Kusumojanto, and Indrawati (2021) investigated if entrepreneurship education, the need for achievement, creativity, and entrepreneurial self-efficacy can influence entrepreneurial intentions. The study adopted a quantitative methodology. Path analysis was used to gather and analyze the data. The findings revealed that entrepreneurship education, achievement needs, creativity, and self-efficacy can all have an impact on one's entrepreneurial intentions.

The mediation role of innovative activity in the link between entrepreneurial self-efficacy and entrepreneurial intention was examined by NoreaChavez (2020). He used a survey study design, choosing 358 proprietors of large and medium-sized businesses in a Peruvian textile cluster. He collected data and used partial least squares structural equation modeling to analyze it (PLSSEM). According to his research, the relationship between entrepreneurial self-efficacy and entrepreneurial intention is significantly mediated by inventive activity.

Elitha and Purba (2020) looked at the link between entrepreneurial self-efficacy (ESE) and entrepreneurial intention (EI). They used a survey research strategy. They obtained data from 299 participants. Descriptive statistics, a correlation matrix, and a SEM model were used to analyze the data. Their findings demonstrated that entrepreneurial intentional self-regulation (EISR) fully moderated the association between entrepreneurial self-efficacy and entrepreneurial ambition.

Yang (2019) studied how role models affected entrepreneurial intentions and self-efficacy. He employed a survey research design using 440 samples of university students from China and Korea. Given that the main focus of entrepreneurship research has been on the effects of entrepreneurial education, he looked at the influence and effectiveness of role models on promoting entrepreneurship. For data analysis, he employed correlations, hierarchical regression, and descriptive statistics. His research showed that entrepreneurial self-efficacy and

intention were positively influenced by their role models. Also, entrepreneurial self-efficacy had a significant and positive relationship with entrepreneurial intention.

The impact of entrepreneurial self-efficacy on students' entrepreneurial intentions was studied by Wang and Huang (2019). The research design for the study was survey. Data were collected from 870 students, and they were analyzed using regression analysis, descriptive statistics, and Pearson product-moment correlation. According to the study's findings, entrepreneurial self-efficacy considerably and favorably predicted entrepreneurial intentions, while social support favorably tempered this effect. A theoretical and practical reference for enhancing the entrepreneurial intentions of university students is presented, according to the study's findings.

Methodology

This study took survey research design into account. In Edo State, two-in-one aggregated study groups were found through this research; these are small and medium-sized businesses. In total, Edo State has 2,677 small and medium-sized businesses. These SMEs were recognized as such by the State. Multistage sampling procedure was determined using statistical estimating technique of Sallant and Dillman's (1997) method. The formula used for this investigation. Surveys were conducted on SME owner/managers. The size of the sample was is stated below:

$$N_s = \frac{N_p (p)(1 - p)}{(N_p - 1) \left(\frac{B}{C}\right)^2 + (p)(1 - p)}$$

Where:

Ns= completed sample size required

Np= Sample population

P= proportion expected to answer in a certain way (50% or 0.5 is most conservative)

B= acceptable level of sampling error (0.05 = ±5%; 0.03 = ± 3%)

C= Z statistic (1.960=95% confidence level)

The study used a 336-participants sample size. As a result, the survey was conducted in Edo State using a sample size of 336 respondents. Both descriptive and inferential analytical techniques were used to analyze the study's data. Multiple regression analysis is the basic analytical method that was used. The models are specified as follows:

$$EI (PTA) = a + b_1INA + b_2PUU + b_3FMC + b_4MKA + b_5INC + b_6RKT + b_7CLT + e \dots\dots\dots 1$$

Where,

PTA = Propensity to Act

EI = Entrepreneurial Intentions (dependent variable); a = constant

CLT= Critical Thinking

INA= Information Alertness

PUU= Planning Under Uncertainty

FMC= Financial Management Capability

MKA= Marketing Ability

INC= Innovation Capability RKT= Risk-Taking b₁, b₂, b₃, ..., ..., ..., ...,b₇ are regression coefficients e =

Stochastic term

Taking start-up of own business as being too risky	336	2.0893	1.10267
Seeking entrepreneurial challenge	336	2.1161	1.13883

Data Analysis and Discussion

Table 1 Descriptive statistics of attitude towards entrepreneurship

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation
Improving product differentiation	336	2.1280	1.11636
Consideration for entrepreneurship as a good career option	336	2.1935	1.12027

Source: Field Survey (2021)

Table 1 shows the descriptive statistics of attitude towards entrepreneurship. The table shows improving product differentiation (\bar{x} = 2.1280; SD = 1.11636). This implies that respondents develop reasonable attitude towards entrepreneurship in Edo State. The result shows consideration for entrepreneurship as a good career option (\bar{x} = 2.1935; SD = 1.12027). The strength of the mean score reveals that respondents’ attitude towards making entrepreneurship as a good career option is high. The results show taking start-up of own business as being too risky (\bar{x} = 2.0893; SD = 1.10267) and seeking entrepreneurial challenge (\bar{x} = 2.1161; SD = 1.13883). The attitude of respondents towards seeking entrepreneurial challenge is higher.

Table 2 Descriptive statistics of venture creation and entrepreneurial performance N

Plans to create a new business venture	336
Starting a new business	336
Taking advantage of available opportunities by creating new business	336
New venture performance is measured by the average gross profit	336
New venture performance is measured by absolute growth in sales	336
New venture performance is measured by growth in market share	336

Source: Field Survey (2021)

Table 2 shows that respondents have laid down plan to create a new business venture (\bar{x} = 3.1012; SD = 1.45023); respondents have already started a new business (\bar{x} = 3.2113; SD = 1.43516); respondents want take advantage of available opportunities by creating new business (\bar{x} = 3.1310; SD = 1.52025); respondents’ new venture performance is measured by the average gross profit (\bar{x} = 2.4762; SD = 1.39702); respondents’ new venture performance is measured by absolute growth in sales (\bar{x} = 2.7738; SD = 1.48305); and respondents’ new venture performance is measured by growth in market share (\bar{x} = 2.9881; SD = 1.47005). The implication of these results is that respondents have business ventures and their entrepreneurial performances are measurable.

Table 3a Model Summary on the effect of selfefficacy on the propensity to act of SME Owners in

Edo State

Model	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.898 ^a	.806	.65391
2	.908 ^b	.825	.62237
3	.911 ^c	.830	.61356
4	.920 ^d	.846	.58464
5	.926 ^e	.858	.56246
6	.928 ^f	.861	.55674
7Mean		.929 ^g	Std. Deviation .863

Predictors: 3.1012 (Constant), Information Alertness, 1.45023 Innovation Capability, Risk3.2113 1.43516-Taking Capability, Planning Under Uncertainty, Marketing Ability, 3.1310 1.52025 Financial Management Capability, Critical Thinking

Table 2.47623a shows the results on the effect of self-1.39702 -efficacy on the propensity to act of SME Owners in Edo State. The 2.7738Stepwise Multiple 1.48305Regression considered the individual explanatory power of the variables (such as opportunity 2.9881 identification 1.47005& creativity, information alertness, planning under uncertainty, financial management capability, marketing ability, managerial competence, innovation capability, risk-taking capability and critical thinking) relating to entrepreneurial self-efficacy of SME owners in Edo State. The results show information alertness ($R^2= 0.806$), innovation capability ($R^2= 0.825$), risk-taking capability ($R^2= 0.830$), planning under uncertainty ($R^2= 0.846$), marketing ability ($R^2= 0.858$), financial management capability ($R^2= 0.861$) and critical thinking ($R^2= 0.863$). Information alertness accounts for 80.6% variations in the propensity to act of SME Owners in Edo State; innovation capability accounts for 82.5% variations; risk-taking capability accounts for 83% variations; planning under uncertainty accounts for 84.6% variations; marketing ability accounts for 85.8% variations; financial management capability accounts for

86.1% variations; and critical thinking accounts for 86.3% variations. The remaining unaccounted variations for the individual variables in the model indicate that there are provisions for other variables to also explain the **Dependent Variable: Propensity to Act**

Variations in the propensity to act of SME Owners in Edo State.

Table 3b ANOVA on the effect of self-efficacy on the propensity to act of SME Owners in Edo State

Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	592.181	1	592.181	1384.886	.000 ^b
	Residual	142.819	334	.428		
	Total	735.000	335			
2	Regression	606.015	2	303.007	782.270	.000 ^c
	Residual	128.985	333	.387		
	Total	735.000	335			
3	Regression	610.017	3	203.339	540.144	.000 ^d
	Residual	124.983	332	.376		
	Total	735.000	335			
4	Regression	621.865	4	155.466	454.847	.000 ^e
	Residual	113.135	331	.342		
	Total	735.000	335			
5	Regression	630.601	5	126.120	398.661	.000 ^f
	Residual	104.399	330	.316		
	Total	735.000	335			
6	Regression	633.024	6	105.504	340.383	.000 ^g
	Residual	101.976	329	.310		
	Total	735.000	335			
7	Regression	634.311	7	90.616	295.186	.000 ^h
	Residual	100.689	328	.307		
	Total	735.000	335			

Predictors: (Constant), Information Alertness, Innovation Capability, Risk-Taking Capability, Planning Under Uncertainty, Marketing Ability, Financial Management Capability, Critical Thinking

Table 3b shows the levels of variability within the regression models and forms the basis for tests of significance. The ANOVA table also reports that using the model is better than guessing the mean. The mean square residual values (0.428 for information alertness, 0.387 for innovation capability, 0.376 for risk-taking capability, 0.342 for planning under uncertainty, 0.316 for marketing ability, 0.310 for financial management capability, and 0.307 for critical thinking) are small, indicating less deviation between the observed and fitted values. The P-value for the F test statistic (1384.886 for information alertness, 782.270 for innovation capability, 540.144 for risk-taking capability, 454.847 for planning under uncertainty, 398.661 for marketing ability, 340.383 for financial management capability, and 295.186 for critical thinking) are less than 0.001, providing strong evidence against the null hypotheses. The coefficient of determination (in table 3a) for **Dependent Variable: Propensity to Act**

Table 3c shows that information alertness has linear relationship with the propensity to act of SME Owners in Edo State (given $\beta = 0.641$; Sig-value < 0.01). the result shows that 64.1% increase in information alertness will lead to about 64.1% increase in propensity to act of SME Owners in Edo State. The variable (information alertness) entered the model with positive sign; implying that significant but positive linear relationship exists between information alertness and the propensity to act of SME Owners in Edo State.

The table shows that innovation capability (with $\beta = 0.424$; Sig-value < 0.01) has linear relationship with the propensity to act of SME Owners in Edo State. The linear relationship is positive based on the sign. This implies information alertness ($R^2 = 0.806$), innovation capability ($R^2 = 0.825$), risk-taking capability ($R^2 = 0.830$), planning under uncertainty ($R^2 = 0.846$), marketing ability ($R^2 =$ Critical thinking ($R^2 = 0.863$) indicate significant effect on the propensity to act of SME Owners in Edo State.

0.858), financial management capability ($R^2 = 0.861$) and

Table 3c Coefficients on the effect of self-efficacy on the propensity to act of SME Owners in Edo State

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	-.179	.086		-2.075	.039
Information Alertness	.641	.036	.617	17.561	.000
Innovation Capability	.424	.054	.354	7.802	.000
Risk-Taking Capability	.249	.055	.249	4.553	.000
Planning Under Uncertainty	-.623	.172	-.440	-3.632	.000
Marketing Ability	.693	.111	.488	6.256	.000
Financial Management Capability	-.461	.160	-.344	-2.882	.004
Critical Thinking	.097	.048	.094	2.047	.041

that 42.4% increase in innovation capability of SME owners will lead to direct proportional increase in their propensity to act in Edo State. The positive linear relationship between innovation capability of SME owners and their propensity to act in Edo State is significant.

The result shows that risk-taking capability (with $\beta = 0.249$; Sig-value < 0.01) has linear relationship with the propensity to act of SME Owners in Edo State. The model shows that the result for risk-taking capability is positive. This implies that 24.9% increase in risk-taking capability will lead to about the same 24.9% increase in the propensity to act of SME Owners in Edo State. The result however shows that the positive linear relationship between the risk-taking capability of SME Owners and their propensity to act is significant.

The table shows that planning under uncertainty has negative linear relationship with the propensity to act of SME Owners in Edo State (given $\beta = -0.623$; Sig-value < 0.01). The result implies that 62.3% increase in planning under uncertainty will result in about 62.3% decrease in the propensity to act of SME Owners in Edo State. The Sig-value shows that the negative linear relationship between planning under uncertainty and the propensity to act of SME Owners in Edo State is significant. The table shows that marketing ability has positive linear relationship with the propensity to act of SME Owners in Edo State (given $\beta = 0.693$; Sig-value < 0.01). The result implies that 69.3% increase in marketing ability will bring about proportional increase in the propensity to act of SME Owners in Edo State. The Sig-value shows that the positive linear relationship between marketing ability and the propensity to act of SME Owners in Edo State is significant.

The table shows that financial management capability (with $\beta = -0.461$; Sig-value < 0.01) has linear relationship with the propensity to act of SME Owners in Edo State. The linear relationship is negative based on the sign. This implies that 46.1% increase in financial management capability of SME owners will lead to proportional decrease in their propensity to act in Edo State. The negative linear relationship between financial management capability of SME owners and their propensity to act in Edo State is significant.

The table shows that critical thinking has linear relationship with the propensity to act of SME Owners in Edo State (given $\beta = 0.097$; Sig-value < 0.05). The result shows that 9.7% increase in critical thinking will bring about proportional increase in propensity to act of SME Owners in Edo State. The variable (critical thinking) entered the model with positive sign; showing that significant but positive linear relationship exists between critical thinking and the propensity to act of SME Owners in Edo State.

Discussion of Findings

Finding showed that self-efficacy has effect on the propensity to act of SME Owners in Edo State. The explanatory power of the individual constructs relating entrepreneurial self-efficacy of SME owners in Edo State was established. Finding showed that information alertness has contributes strongly to the propensity to act of SME Owners in Edo State. Li, Murad, Shahzad, Khan, Ashraf, and Dogbe (2020) posited information alertness is key to knowledge, and the adequate amount of this can drive favourable entrepreneurial behaviour. In other words increase in information alertness will drive increase in propensity to act in entrepreneurship. Innovation capability has significant positive contribution to the propensity to act of SME Owners in Edo State. This means that a 42.4% increase in SME owners' innovation capability will result in a decisive marked increase in their propensity to act in Edo State. There is a considerable positive linear link between SME owners' innovative capability and their propensity to act. Finding showed that risk-taking capability also has significant positive contribution to the propensity to act of SME Owners in Edo State. SME Owners with risktaking capability has the necessary skill to estimate the possibility of achieving entrepreneurial success. They will be able to deal with limited knowledge and act on a risky alternative that demands expertise in order to achieve demanding but achievable goals. An increase in risk-taking skill will contribute to a similar increase in SME Owners' inclination to act. The finding demonstrates that there is a considerable positive linear link between SME Owners' risk-taking capacity and their propensity to act.

Also findings showed that critical thinking and marketing ability have linear relationship with the propensity to act of SME Owners in Edo State. The contribution of marketing ability to propensity to act is higher (69.3%) than that of self-efficacy in critical thinking (9.7%). It is however found that both have significant positive linear relationship with the propensity to act of SME Owners in Edo State is significant. Contrarily, financial

management capability and planning under uncertainty were found to have significant negative linear relationship with the propensity to act of SME Owners in Edo State.

Conclusion and Recommendation Entrepreneurial self-efficacy can stimulate the propensity to act of SME Owners in Edo State. Self-efficacy has an impact on SME owners' willingness to act. Opportunity identification and creativity, information alertness, planning under uncertainty, financial management capability, marketing ability, managerial competence, innovation capability, risk-taking capability, and critical thinking are all factors that influence SME Owners' willingness to act in Edo State.

The study recommended that SMEDAN should prioritize the need for consistent entrepreneurial self-efficacy for SME owners to increase their level of propensity to act in Edo State. To achieve consistent entrepreneurial self-efficacy for SME owners, effort should be geared towards improved opportunity identification & creativity, information alertness, marketing ability, managerial competence, innovation capability, risk-taking capability and critical thinking. Less attention should be given to planning under uncertainty and financial management capability on a scale of importance. These need high level of scientific orientations and can be outsourced.

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